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IMPACT OF PURPOSIVE READING AMONG ENGLISH MAJORS OF THE COLLEGE OF EDUCATION AT THE MINDANAO STATE UNIVERSITY – SULU

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the impact of purposive reading among English majors of the College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu during the Academic Year 2023-2024. With 100 samples taken through non-probability sampling method via purposive sampling, and with the use of weighted mean, standard deviation, t-test for independent samples, one-way ANOVA, and Pearson's r, this study revealed the following findings: 1) Student-respondents involved in this study are mostly female, within 18-19 years old, and mostly enrolled as second and third year levels; 2) On the average, there is a high extent of the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu; 3) Generally, except for year level, variables age and gender do not significantly mediate in ways how student-respondents assessed the extent of the impact of purposive reading among English majors of the College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu; 4) Generally, the group of student-respondents who assessed the extent of impact of purposive reading among English majors of the College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu in terms of *evaluation* as **Most of the Time** is probably the same group of student-respondents who assessed the *knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, and synthesis* as **Most of the Time**, respectively; and 5) This study seems to support the Reader Response Theory which stresses that readers focus on the text, finding all meaning, the value in reading materials and regarding everything else as extraneous, including readers.

KEYWORDS: *purposive reading, English majors, Reader Response Theory, Mindanao State University-Sulu*

INTRODUCTION

The world of academia and professional communication hinges upon the mastery of language, and for college students majoring in English, reading purposively emerges as a fundamental cornerstone of their educational journey. This practice holds profound implications, transcending the bounds of mere comprehension to shape their linguistic competence, purposive thinking abilities, and intellectual growth. This study serves as a gateway into the exploration of how purposive reading profoundly influences College of Education Major in English Students at Mindanao State University – Sulu, illuminating its role as a catalyst for academic excellence and personal enrichment.

Purposive reading is a deliberate and intentional practice, one that empowers students to navigate a diverse landscape of literary classics, scholarly treatises and many others. Leute (2022) states that deriving a sense of purpose from an activity also promotes a person's engagement, while continued practice promotes growth in the development of a particular skill. This exploration delves into the intricate relationship between the practice of purposive reading and its effects, shedding light on the multifaceted ways in which this seemingly simple pursuit can influence formal education.

When transactions between humans are made through writing, some instances occur when those exchanges come close to any oral conversations. And to effectively hold up their end of the conversation, purposively sifting through words, and creating meaning from what has been stated, results to inevitably collecting the meaning through the said interaction. Understanding the impact of this process and how this possibly occurs to the Language Students will help further the academicians improve the curriculum on how instructions for L1, and L2 and others.

In a study launched by Roomy (2022), he said reading with a sense of purpose is an indispensable learning skill that students need both inside and outside the classroom. Rommy (2022) added that there are significant effects of purposive reading skills on students' reading comprehension at different levels. Students viewed reading as an active dynamic process that motivated the activation of higher order thinking skills and helped students tap into their prior experiences to approach the reading materials.

The democratization and commodification of education has witnessed an increase in postgraduate education as it is one of the main sources contributing to the advancement of knowledge, technology, and innovation (Shamida and Nawi, 2021). The 21st century requires that every individual has a purposive ability to receive, process, and understand diverse information (Setiwan & Gusdian, 2021).

This study is to promote reading practices among language students, by further scrutinizing the importance of comprehension, knowledge, application, analysis and

synthesis. For these strategies encompass the relationship that is made in order to successfully comprehend through the process of reading.

Research Questions

The study assessed the impact of purposive reading among English Majors of College of Education at the Mindanao State University–Sulu. Specifically, it sought to answer to each of the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of student-respondents as to:
 - 1.1.1 age;
 - 1.1.2 gender; and
 - 1.1.3 year level?

2. What is the extent of impact of purposive reading among English Majors College of Education at Mindanao State University – Sulu in terms of:
 - 2.1.1 knowledge;
 - 2.1.2 comprehension;
 - 2.1.3 application;
 - 2.1.4 analysis;
 - 2.1.5 synthesis; and
 - 2.1.6 evaluation?

3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of impact of purposive reading among English Majors College of Education at Mindanao State University – Sulu when classified into:
 - 3.1.1 age;
 - 3.1.2 gender; and
 - 3.1.3 year level?

4. Is there a significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the impact of purposive reading among College of Education Major in English students at Mindanao State University – Sulu?

METHODOLOGY

This chapter deals with the research method that was employed in the conduct of this study. It focuses on the research design, locale, respondents of the study, sampling design, data gathering procedure, research instrument, validity and reliability, and statistical treatments of data.

Research Design

The study focused on the impact of Purposive Reading among the College of Education Major in English Students at the Mindanao State University–Sulu. The program is adapted by MSU System Learning Modality following the contextualized Commission on Higher Education Outcome Based Syllabus of the English Majors. A descriptive survey design was utilized adopting the intention to gather information from sample of the individuals regarding issues and relationships affecting a larger group known as the population, and then generalized as the total population.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in the Mindanao State University–Sulu, specifically among the College of Education Major in English students during the second semester of the school year 2023-2024.

Respondents of the Study

The research population consists of around 400 students of the English Department of the MSU-Sulu College of Education. A sample of 100 students, representing 25% of the target population.

Table 1. Distribution of samples according to the year level

Year Level	Total
1 st Year	10
2 nd Year	40
3 rd Year	42
4 th Year	8
Grand Total	100

Sampling Design

A purposive sampling method was employed in this study. The use of purposive sampling in this study was to ensure that representation of all the sub-categories under the profiles.

Data Gathering Procedure

The Data gathering and instrumentation process was conducted using the survey questionnaire. The survey questionnaire consisted of two sections. Section A explored the demographic variables of the learners, whereas section B incorporated 44 items that related to the learners' purposive reading practices. The survey questionnaire instrument was used to obtain data about the learners' self-perceived ability to use purposive reading strategies in the classroom. To assist the researchers to understand the learners' self-

perceived and self-rated purposive reading practices, the closed questions were prepared.

The questionnaire contained opinion statements categorized as close questions, which measured on a four-point Likert scale: (1) Never, (2) Sometimes, (3) Most of the time and (4) Always. These intensity scales were used to simplify the procedure of data processing and to obtain uniformity. Furthermore, the opinion statements were kept simple, relevant and precise so that each learner could understand. The questionnaire was distributed among the learners from the MSU-Sulu College of Education English Department intended for self-ratings on their self-perceived purposive reading ability.

The following steps were followed in the course of data gathering:

- 1.) A permit to administer the questionnaire was sought from the Office of the Dean of the MSU-Sulu College of Education, and the Chancellor of the said institution.
- 2.) The launching and administering as well as the retrieval of the questionnaire was conducted personally with utmost ethical practice by the researcher.

Research Instruments

Quantitative method was used for the analysis of the study. According to Maree (2007), quantitative research is a process that is systematic and objective in its ways of using numerical data from only a selected subgroup of a universe (or population) to generalize the findings to the universe that is being studied

To acquire genuine and relevant data for the study, a non-observational approach with a Survey Questionnaire was used as the research instrument. Each respondent answered a two-part adapted questionnaire from Anderson and Krathwohli (2001).

Survey Questionnaires (SQ) I and II are separate. SQ I dealt with respondents' personal information such as gender, age and year level addressing research question number 1. SQ II is broken down into another section which dealt reading strategies that students use, therefore addressing research question 2.

Validity and Reliability

To ensure the successful execution of the study, the researcher adapted a standardized questionnaire survey in order to evaluate different variables in purposive reading. However, to guarantee its usability applicable to the local context of the respondents, modifications were made and these were subjected to the perusal of at least two experts from the faculty members of the School of Graduate Studies of the Sulu State College. This checklist covered all types of strategies relevant to a students' academic pursuit whilst purposely reading.

Statistical Treatment of The Data

Obtaining the empirical data on the four research questions, the following statistical tools were utilized. The data gathered from the instruments were treated statistically.

1. For research problem number 1, in analyzing the data for the demographic profile of students in terms of age, gender, and year level, Frequency and Percentage were used.
2. For research problem number 2, the relativity of each variable in the impact of purposive reading were analyzed through weighted mean and standard deviation.
3. For research problem number 3, t-test for independent samples was used to compare the means between two groups for gender, whereas one-way ANOVA was used to compare the means among the strategies.
4. For research problem number 4, Pearson r was used to measure the strength and direction of the relationship between each variable, of which shall answer the inferential question: "Is there a significant correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the impact of purposive reading among College of Education Major in English Students at Mindanao State University – Sulu?"

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section deals with the presentations, analyses and interpretations of results based on the data obtained for this study. Explicitly, it presents student-respondents' demographic profiles in terms of age, gender, and year level; the extent of the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu; the significant correlation and differences in the extent of the impact of purposive reading among English majors when data are grouped according student-respondents' demographic profile.

Based on the thorough, proper scoring and statistical treatments of data gathered for this study, the following are the presentations, analyses and interpretations of results which correspond to each of the research questions:

Table 1.1 Demographic profile of the student-respondents in terms of age

Age	Number of Students	Percent
17 years old & below	0	0
18-19 years old	80	80.0%
20 years old & above	20	20.0%
Total	100	100%

Table 1.1 presents the demographic profile of the student-respondents in terms of age. It can be gleaned from this table that out of 100 student-respondents, 80 (80.0%) are within 18-19 years old, 20 (20.0%) are within 20 years old & above, and none is within

17 years old & below. This means that more than three-fourth or great majority of the student-respondents involved in this study are within 18-19 years old. This result implies that almost all of the student-respondents involved in this study are at the ideal age range for college students.

Table 1.2 Demographic profile of the student-respondents in terms of gender

Gender	Number of Students	Percent
Male	29	29.0%
Female	71	71.0%
Total	100	100%

Table 1.2 shows the demographic profile of the student-respondents in terms of gender. It can be gleaned from this table that out of 100 student-respondents, 29 (29.0%) are male and 71 (71.0%) are female. This means that nearly three-fourth or great majority of the student-respondents involved in this study are female which is far higher in number than male respondents.

Table 1.3 Demographic profile of the student-respondents in terms of year level

Year Level	Number of Students	Percent
First Year	10	10.0%
Second Year	40	40.0%
Third Year	42	42.0%
Fourth Year	8	8.0%
Total	100	100%

Table 1.3 presents the demographic profile of the student-respondents in terms of grade level. It can be gleaned from this table that out of 100 student-respondents, 10 (10.0%) are enrolled as First Year, 40 (40.0%) are enrolled as Second Year, 42 (42.0%) are enrolled as Third Year, and 8 (8.0%) are enrolled as Fourth Year level, respectively. This result implies that student-respondents involved in this study are mostly represented by Second Year and Third Year levels.

Table 2. Extent of the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu in terms of knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis, and evaluation

Impact of Purposive Reading				
Knowledge		Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	I can remember the information from a text that I have read.	2.7800	.73278	Most of the time
2	I can identify specific terms in a text.	2.7000	.68902	Most of the time
3	I can identify main ideas in a text.	2.7800	.77303	Most of the time
4	I can identify supporting details in a text.	2.6800	.72307	Most of the time

5	I have an in-depth knowledge and can teach others.	2.5400	.74427	Most of the time
Total Weighted Mean		2.6960	.58498	Most of the time
Comprehension		Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	I can read and understand the title of a text.	3.4000	.60302	Most of the time
2	I can quickly read through long and difficult texts, locating relevant details.	2.9600	.76436	Most of the time
3	I can describe the main ideas in a text.	2.9700	.74475	Most of the time
4	I can describe supporting details in a text.	2.8500	.72995	Most of the time
5	I can explain the meaning of words, or sentences from the context.	2.9200	.72027	Most of the time
Total Weighted Mean		3.0200	.56318	Most of the time
Application		Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	I can predict the outcomes of an article.	2.6200	.76251	Most of the time
2	I can use the knowledge that I have when I read a text	3.0800	.74779	Most of the time
3	I can use my personal experiences to improve my understanding of a text when I read.	3.1600	.69224	Most of the time
4	I can read about an idea in a text and use it in other situations that I read about.	2.9100	.76667	Most of the time
5	I can read about an idea in a text and use it to solve problems in my own life	2.8500	.72995	Most of the time
Total Weighted Mean		2.9240	.57474	Most of the time
Analysis		Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	When I read a text, I know the difference between a fact and an opinion	3.1300	.67652	Most of the time
2	When I read a text, I can show which points are relevant to the topic written about.	3.0200	.73828	Most of the time
3	When I read a text, I can conclude what the text is about.	2.9400	.72223	Most of the time
4	When I read a text, I can identify the reasons for certain actions in the text.	2.9400	.73608	Most of the time
5	When I read, I can separate the idea within the text into its different parts	2.8700	.73382	Most of the time
Total Weighted Mean		2.9800	.57314	Most of the time
Synthesis		Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	I can connect the ideas within a sentence.	3.0600	.78907	Most of the time
2	I can connect the ideas between paragraphs	2.9100	.75338	Most of the time

3	I can connect ideas between different reading materials.	2.9000	.77198	Most of the time
4	I can summarize information after reading a text	3.1000	.78496	Most of the time
5	I can draw conclusion after reading a text.	3.0400	.76436	Most of the time
Total Weighted Mean		3.0020	.65843	Most of the time
Evaluation		Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	I can decide on the trustworthiness of the information in a text.	2.9600	.72363	Most of the time
2	I can make a decision on the argument when I read.	3.0600	.76303	Most of the time
3	I can determine the strength of an idea in a text.	2.9700	.70288	Most of the time
4	I can determine the weakness of an idea in a text.	2.9500	.74366	Most of the time
5	I can determine the relevancy of an idea in a text.	3.0800	.76118	Most of the time
Total Weighted Mean		3.0040	.61364	Most of the time
Overall Total weighted Mean		2.9337	.59468	Most of the time

Legend: (4) 3.50 – 4.00=Always (A); (3) 2.50 – 3.49=Most of the Time (MA); (2) 1.50 – 2.49=Sometimes (S); (1) 1.00 – 1.49=Never (N)

Table 2 shows the extent of the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu in terms of Knowledge, Comprehension, Application, Analysis, Synthesis, and Evaluation. As shown in this table, this category obtained an overall total weighted mean score of **2.9337** with standard deviation of .59468 which is rated as **Most of the Time**. This result reveals that student-respondents implored that English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu when engage in purposive reading, are most of the time they tend to remember the information from a text that they have read, read and understand the title of the text, predict the outcomes of an article, know the difference between a fact and an opinion, connect the ideas within a sentence, and decide on the trustworthiness of the information in a text.

Specifically, student-respondents rated as Most of the time the following items: “I can remember the information from a text that I have read”, “I can read and understand the title of the text”, “I can predict the outcomes of an article”, “When I read a text, I know the difference between a fact and an opinion”, “I can connect the ideas within a sentence”, and “I can decide on the trustworthiness of the information in a text”.

Table 3.1 Differences in the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu when the data are classified according to age

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Knowledge	Between Groups	.006	1	.006	.019	.892	Not Significant
	Within Groups	33.872	98	.346			
	Total	33.878	99				
Comprehension	Between Groups	.123	1	.123	.384	.537	Not Significant
	Within Groups	31.277	98	.319			
	Total	31.400	99				
Application	Between Groups	.000	1	.000	.001	.972	Not Significant
	Within Groups	32.702	98	.334			
	Total	32.702	99				
Analysis	Between Groups	.063	1	.063	.189	.665	Not Significant
	Within Groups	32.457	98	.331			
	Total	32.520	99				
Synthesis	Between Groups	.026	1	.026	.058	.809	Not Significant
	Within Groups	42.894	98	.438			
	Total	42.920	99				
Evaluation	Between Groups	.102	1	.102	.270	.605	Not Significant
	Within Groups	37.176	98	.379			
	Total	37.278	99				

*Significant alpha .05

Table 3.1 presents the differences in the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu when the data are classified according to age. It can be gleaned from this table that the value of F-ratios and *P*-values of all the sub-categories subsumed under the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu are not significant at alpha .05. This means that, although student-respondents vary in age range, still they do not differ in their assessment towards the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu. This result implies that being older or within 20 years old & above may not necessarily put a student-respondent in a vantage point towards assessing the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu than those who are within 17 years old & below, and 18-19 years old, or vice versa.

Nonetheless, it is safe to say that variable age has no significant mediation in ways how student-respondents assessed the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu. Therefore, the

hypothesis which states that “There is no significant difference in the extent of the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of age” is accepted.

Table 3.2 Differences in the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu when the data are classified according to gender

VARIABLES		Mean	S. D.	Mean Difference	t	Sig.	Description
Knowledge	Male	2.9241	.67700	.32132*	2.561	.012	Significant
	Female	2.6028	.51988				
Comprehension	Male	3.1517	.58225	.18553	1.504	.136	Not Significant
	Female	2.9662	.55031				
Application	Male	3.0483	.57235	.17504	1.388	.168	Not Significant
	Female	2.8732	.57195				
Analysis	Male	3.0966	.57724	.16416	1.304	.195	Not Significant
	Female	2.9324	.56865				
Synthesis	Male	3.1655	.70725	.23031	1.600	.113	Not Significant
	Female	2.9352	.63044				
Evaluation	Male	3.2000	.68661	.27606*	2.075	.041	Significant
	Female	2.9239	.56706				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

Table 3.2 shows the differences in the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu when the data are classified according to gender. It can be gleaned from this table that, except for “Knowledge” and “Evaluation” value of Mean Differences of all other sub-categories subsumed under the extent of the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu are not significant at alpha .05. This means that male and female student-respondents do not differ in their assessment towards the extent of the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu. This result implies that being a male student-respondent may not necessarily put him in a vantage point towards assessing the extent of the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu than his female counterpart, or vice versa. Consequently, it is safe to say that variable gender has no significant influence in the ways how student-respondents assessed the extent of the impact of purposive reading

among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu Therefore, the hypothesis which states that “There is no significant difference in the extent of the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of gender” is accepted.

Table 3.3 Differences in the extent of the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu when the data are classified according to year level

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Knowledge	Between Groups	6.599	3	2.200	7.741*	.000	Significant
	Within Groups	27.279	96	.284			
	Total	33.878	99				
Comprehension	Between Groups	6.459	3	2.153	8.288*	.000	Significant
	Within Groups	24.941	96	.260			
	Total	31.400	99				
Application	Between Groups	5.780	3	1.927	6.870*	.000	Significant
	Within Groups	26.923	96	.280			
	Total	32.702	99				
Analysis	Between Groups	3.649	3	1.216	4.044*	.009	Significant
	Within Groups	28.871	96	.301			
	Total	32.520	99				
Synthesis	Between Groups	6.198	3	2.066	5.401*	.002	Significant
	Within Groups	36.722	96	.383			
	Total	42.920	99				
Evaluation	Between Groups	4.556	3	1.519	4.455*	.006	Significant
	Within Groups	32.722	96	.341			
	Total	37.278	99				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

Table 3.3 shows the differences in the extent of the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu when the data are classified according to year level. It can be gleaned from this table that value of F-ratios and *P*-values of all the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu are indeed significant at alpha .05. This means that, the fact that student-respondents vary in year level indeed they differ in their assessment towards the extent of the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu. This result implies that being a Fourth Year level may probably put a student-respondent in a vantage point towards assessing the extent of the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu than those enrolled as First Year, Second Year, and Third Year level, vice versa.

Consequently, it is safe to say that variable year level has indeed a significant influence in the ways how student-respondents assessed the extent of the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that “There is no significant difference in the extent of the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of year level” is rejected.

Table 3.3.1 Post Hoc Analysis: Differences in the extent of the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu when the data are classified according to year level

Dependent Variables	(I) Grouping by Year Level	(J) Grouping by Year Level	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
<i>Knowledge</i>	First Year	Second Year	-.14000	.18847	.879
		Third Year	-.04571	.18757	.995
		Fourth Year	-1.01000*	.25286	.001
<i>Comprehension</i>	Second Year	First Year	-.11500	.18021	.919
		Third Year	.33357*	.11261	.020
		Fourth Year	-.54500*	.19741	.034
<i>Application</i>	First Year	Second Year	.01500	.18723	1.000
		Third Year	.20762	.18634	.682
		Fourth Year	-.71500*	.25120	.027
<i>Analysis</i>	Third Year	First Year	-.02667	.19296	.999
		Second Year	-.22167	.12116	.266
		Fourth Year	-.69167*	.21155	.008
<i>Synthesis</i>	Third Year	First Year	-.38286	.21762	.299
		Second Year	-.34286	.13664	.065
		Fourth Year	-.86786*	.23858	.002
<i>Evaluation</i>	Third Year	First Year	-.38571	.20543	.245
		Second Year	-.22571	.12899	.304
		Fourth Year	-.76071*	.22522	.006

* The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

A Post Hoc Analysis using Tukey Test was conducted to determine which among groups classified according to year level to have different levels of mean in areas subsumed under the extent of the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu when the data are classified according to year level.

The result of the analysis which is shown in Table 3.3.1 indicates that the difference in the means of knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis, and evaluation is obtained by way of lower group mean minus higher group mean.

On Knowledge: It shows that the group of student-respondents enrolled as Fourth Year obtained the mean difference of -1.01000^* with Standard Error of .25286 and p-value of .001 which is significant at $\alpha=.05$ over the group of student-respondents enrolled as First Year level. So, under this sub-category, no other group of student-respondents are supposed to have better ways of assessing the extent of the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu in terms of Knowledge than those student-respondents who are enrolled as Fourth Year level.

On Comprehension: It shows that the group of student-respondents enrolled as Fourth Year obtained the mean difference of $-.54500^*$ with Standard Error of .19741 and p-value of .034 which is significant at $\alpha=.05$ over the group of student-respondents enrolled as Second Year level. So, under this sub-category, no other group of student-respondents are supposed to have better ways of assessing the extent of the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu in terms of Comprehension than those student-respondents who are enrolled as Fourth Year level.

On Application: It shows that the group of student-respondents enrolled as Fourth Year obtained the mean difference of $-.71500^*$ with Standard Error of .25120 and p-value of .027 which is significant at $\alpha=.05$ over the group of student-respondents enrolled as First Year level. So, under this sub-category, no other group of student-respondents are supposed to have better ways of assessing the extent of the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu in terms of Application than those student-respondents who are enrolled as Fourth Year level.

On Analysis: It shows that the group of student-respondents enrolled as Fourth Year obtained the mean difference of $-.69167^*$ with Standard Error of .21155 and p-value of .008 which is significant at $\alpha=.05$ over the group of student-respondents enrolled as Third Year level. So, under this sub-category, no other group of student-respondents are supposed to have better ways of assessing the extent of the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu in terms of Analysis than those student-respondents who are enrolled as Fourth Year level.

On Synthesis: It shows that the group of student-respondents enrolled as Fourth Year obtained the mean difference of $-.86786^*$ with Standard Error of $.23858$ and p-value of $.002$ which is significant at $\alpha=.05$ over the group of student-respondents enrolled as Third Year level. So, under this sub-category, no other group of student-respondents are supposed to have better ways of assessing the extent of the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu in terms of Synthesis than those student-respondents who are enrolled as Fourth Year level.

On Evaluation: It shows that the group of student-respondents enrolled as Fourth Year obtained the mean difference of $-.76071^*$ with Standard Error of $.22522$ and p-value of $.006$ which is significant at $\alpha=.05$ over the group of student-respondents enrolled as Third Year level. So, under this sub-category, no other group of student-respondents are supposed to have better ways of assessing the extent of the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu in terms of Evaluation than those student-respondents who are enrolled as Fourth Year level.

Table 4. Correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu

Variables		Pearson r	Sig	N	Description
Dependent	Independent				
Evaluation	Knowledge	.633**	.000	100	High
	Comprehension	.691**	.000	100	High
	Application	.712**	.000	100	Very High
	Analysis	.723**	.000	100	Very High
	Synthesis	.800**	.000	100	Very High

*Correlation Coefficient is significant at $\alpha .05$

Correlation Coefficient Scales Adopted from Hopkins, Will (2002): 0.0-0.1=Nearly Zero; 0.1-0.30=Low; .3-0.5 0=Moderate; .5-0.7-0=High; .7-0.9= Very High; 0.9-1=Nearly Perfect

Table 4 illustrates the correlation among the categories subsumed under the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu in the contexts of Knowledge, Comprehension, Application, Analysis, Synthesis, and Evaluation. It can be gleaned from this table that the computed Pearson Correlation Coefficients (Pearson r) among these variables are indeed significant at $\alpha .05$.

Specifically, the degrees of correlations among the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu are as follows:

- 1) High positive correlation between Evaluation and Knowledge;

- 2) High positive correlation between Evaluation and Comprehension;
- 3) Very High positive correlation between Evaluation and Application;
- 4) Very High positive correlation between Evaluation and analysis; and
- 5) Very High positive correlation between Evaluation and Synthesis.

These results indicate that the group of student-respondents who assessed the extent of impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu in terms of evaluation as Most of the Time is probably the same group of student-respondents who assessed the Knowledge, Comprehension, Application, Analysis, and Synthesis as Most of the Time, respectively.

For the time being, it is safe to say that, generally the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu is very highly correlated.

Conclusions

This study concludes the following based of the findings above:

- 1) Student-respondents involved in this study are adequately represented in terms of age, gender, and year level.
- 2) On the average, there is a high extent of the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University Sulu.
- 3) Generally, except for year level, variables age and gender do not significantly mediate in ways how student-respondents assessed the extent of the impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University Sulu.
- 4) Generally, the group of student-respondents who assessed the extent of impact of purposive reading among English majors of College of Education at Mindanao State University-Sulu in terms of Evaluation as Most of the Time is probably the same group of student-respondents who assessed the Knowledge, Comprehension, Application, Analysis, and Synthesis as Most of the Time, respectively.
- 5) This study seems to support the Reader Response Theory which stresses that readers focus on the text, finding all meaning, the value in reading materials and regarding everything else as extraneous, including readers.

Recommendations

Based on the above findings and conclusions, this study forwards the following recommendations:

- 1) MSU-Sulu administrators may adopt the findings of this study in enhancing the institution's research database in the field of language studies.
- 2) Faculty of MSU-Sulu may utilize the results of this study in identifying best solution in enhancing students' reading comprehension skills.
- 3) College students may use the results of this study in identifying relevant issues and concerns about reading efficiencies.
- 3) Student-researchers in the field of language learning and teaching may replicate this study but to include other variables such as teachers' pedagogical effectiveness,

students' reading proficiency level, and students' language learning proficiency through the use of Information Communication Technology in some other avenues.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

To ensure ethical standards in research is complied, the researcher obtained an informed consent from the respondents. In addition, the researcher assured that privacy of the respondents and the data gathered are safeguarded.

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